

THE LEGAL BASIS OF HIGH PROFESSIONALISM

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Abstract. *The article shows that the problem of the upbringing free, educated and competent professional personnel is possible only by raising the level of their legal culture, legal education and legal consciousness, that is, according to the updated Constitution – in unity, as a direct product of the legal system. It is noted that the legal culture of each specialist consists in a high awareness of the complex of their professional legal acts and that only they are able to provide him with the growth of career professionalism. Several examples show that the formation and improvement of the legal culture of the population is largely determined by operational state policy.*

Keywords: *legal culture, upbringing, legal awareness, competence, professionalism, knowledge.*

Introduction

The problem of raising free, educated and competent professional personnel is possible only by raising the level of their legal culture, legal education and legal consciousness, that is, according to the updated Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in unity, as a direct product of the legal system. The legal culture of each specialist lies in his high awareness of the complex of his professional legal acts. It is argued that only they are able to ensure his career professionalism growth.

The responsible role of the state in the process of forming and raising the legal culture of the population is emphasized. The primary sources of legal regulation of issues of raising the legal culture and legal literacy of the population are the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the dissemination of legal information and ensuring access to it" and "On the radical improvement of the system of raising legal awareness and legal culture in society." They made it possible to determine the main tasks of raising legal awareness and legal culture in society.

Legal culture is a direct product of the legal system

The upbringing of free, educated and competent professional personnel, relying on their own strength, rights and opportunities, independently and consciously approaching the events taking place around them, considering their personal interests in harmony with the interests of the country and the people is a prerequisite for the successful solution of the tasks put forward by the updated Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1].

The high spiritual potential and rich historical heritage of our people were a kind of ideological basis in the updated Constitution. It arose as an expression of public legal awareness and a direct product of the legal system, legal ideology and culture. The Constitution serves as an important factor in the formation of the legal consciousness of the population, its new thinking and culture. Indeed, for this purpose, the Constitution provides (Article 50) the right of everyone to various types of education that can be obtained in the system of continuing education. In addition, the right of citizens to receive higher education at the expense of the state on a competitive basis in state educational organizations is provided (Article 50). The article of the Constitution caused a great resonance, which consolidated the recognition of teacher's work in the Republic of

Uzbekistan as the basis for the development of society and the state, the formation and upbringing of a healthy, harmonious generation, the preservation and enrichment of the spiritual and cultural potential of the people.

It is necessary to overcome in every possible way the manifestation of legal illiteracy, which still exists in our society, to educate respect for the law, to show intolerance to any form of violation of established laws and regulations. Legal upbringing of citizens is an important tool for eliminating these shortcomings.

Legal upbringing is not a simple set of knowledge about human law and formal knowledge of legal issues, but a conscious assimilation of the basic provisions of legislation, the transformation of acquired knowledge into personal trust, strict observance of the law, the fulfillment of which becomes an internal need and daily habit. The most important component of legal upbringing, current issues of legal culture and, in general, legal consciousness are the problem of educating free, educated and competent professional personnel who know their rights, rely on their own strengths and capabilities, independently and consciously approach the events occurring around them, considering personal interests in harmony with the interests of the country and the people.

The legal culture of a specialist is a pledge of honor and respect for his people

It is necessary that every specialist knows the legal acts of his industry and profession well and is able to defend them. Therefore, equipping professional personnel with legal awareness, legal culture and legal knowledge is one of the main tasks of a country building a democratic rule of law state. As long as every member of society does not know and is not aware of their rights, duties and responsibilities, does not consider them as their vital need, our ultimate goal will be meaningless. The legal culture of every specialist in any industry and profession consists, first of all, of high awareness of the complex of all their professional legal acts. This legal knowledge of their field, ultimately, will provide the specialist with unconditional and impeccable application, as well as ensure the growth of career advancement and personal professionalism.

Legal culture is the qualitative application of law in the life of society. This is a kind of barometer in the use of legal opportunities in solving every day, professional problems and issues, in meeting the needs of the people. Legal culture, as an integral part of the general culture of society, is provided by conscious management of society. It is carried out by the competent program tasks set before us, through the coordinated activity of people with full awareness of the fundamental nature of the socio-political reforms carried out in our country [2].

Therefore, the current state of development of society requires a comprehensive improvement of legal culture, legal literacy of all participants in legal relations. Legal culture as a complex of legal knowledge, legal needs and comprehensive practical activities serves to ensure the successful solution of the tasks facing society and the state. A specialist who knows the legal acts of his industry and profession well is always held in high esteem and will enjoy the respect of his people.

The state policy of formation and improvement of the legal culture of the population.

The formation and improvement of the legal culture of the population play an important role in the state policy of Uzbekistan. In ensuring the rule of law, respect for the rights and freedoms of citizens, and in achieving the economic and social progress of the country, issues of strengthening legal culture occupy a special place. The primary sources of legal regulation of issues of improving legal culture and legal literacy of the population are the laws of the Republic

of Uzbekistan "On the dissemination of legal information and ensuring access to it" and "On the provision of legal assistance at the expense of the state". For the first time, the concepts of legal information and access to legal information have been defined at the legislative level. The adoption of the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the fundamental improvement of the system of raising legal awareness and legal culture in society" made it possible to identify the main tasks of raising legal awareness and legal culture in society. It is noted that in the field of improving the legal culture of society, the establishment of the spirit of respect for the laws in it is the key to building a democratic rule of law state and maintaining a balance of personal and public interests.

A number of new provisions on increasing legal awareness and legal culture are reflected in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (05/24/2024) "On further increasing responsibility and forming a compact management system of justice bodies and institutions within the framework of administrative reforms": - in order to increase legal awareness and legal culture of the population, the project "Lawyer Mahalla" is being implemented in the self-government bodies of citizens, - short-term continuous free training courses are organized to improve the legal knowledge and skills of the chairmen of citizens' self-government bodies, - subject Olympiads "Expert in Law" will be held in schools, - Every Wednesday of the week is declared a "Day of legal propaganda" at schools. These political and legal reforms are aimed at improving the legal culture of the population. They aim to build a State governed by the rule of law in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Without the involvement of the broad masses of citizens, government agencies and institutions in the process of improving the legal literacy of the population, it is impossible to embody the idea of "The future of the country belongs to law-abiding and tolerant youth."

Conclusion

The article considers the urgent tasks for the modern era, which is characterized by high mobility of people, extreme variability of our ideas about concepts and morals, national traditions, customs, global technical equipment and information saturation of our everyday life.

The problems of educating free, educated and competent professional personnel are solved in a completely different way - this is only through raising the level of their legal culture, legal education and legal consciousness.

This situation calls for particularly prompt actions by the state and its governing bodies, not only in the field of economic issues, but also in legal law-making activities.

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